

Mass spectrometry in the molecular differentiation between SARS-CoV-2 Spike glycoprotein and mRNA anti COVID-19 vaccine Spike glycoprotein.

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Abstract

SARS-CoV-2 spike proteins, also known as S proteins, are the proteins on the surface of the virus that allow it to bind to and enter host cells. The spike protein binds to the ACE2 receptor on human cells, which allows the virus to enter and infect the host. The spike protein is also the target of many COVID-19 vaccines, as it is a unique and essential component of the virus. These spike proteins are crucial for the virus to infect human cells and replicate. Understanding the structure and function of these spike proteins is important for developing treatments and vaccines for COVID-19. Vaccine spike proteins coded by vaccine mRNA is used to induce the neutral immunity exhibits a sequence difference respect to the virus coded one. In this review we describe the importance of develop test to detect the two different forms in human subjects. Moreover some suggestion of possible method to be used in this field are shown and disclosed

Introduction on the status of knowledge

The natural spike proteins (Sequence shown in Figure 1a) found on the surface of SARS-CoV-2 are the proteins that allow the virus to bind to and enter host cells. These spike proteins have a specific shape and structure that allows them to bind to the ACE2 receptor on human cells.¹ Vaccine spike proteins (Sequence shown in Figure 1b), on the other hand, are synthetic versions of the natural spike proteins that are used in COVID-19 vaccines.²⁻³ These synthetic spike proteins are designed to mimic the natural spike proteins as closely as possible in order to provoke an immune response similar to what would happen after a natural infection.

The difference between natural and vaccine spike proteins is that natural spike proteins are found on the virus surface, while vaccine spike proteins are artificially created for the purpose of vaccination. The natural spike proteins are part of the virus, while the vaccine spike proteins are a replica of it. Another important difference is the presence of two Proline residue in position 986 and 987 respect to lysin (K) and Valin (V) residues present in the protein coded by the virus.

It is important to distinguish between virus spike proteins and vaccine spike proteins when analyzing them in blood because they have different implications for the individual's health. Virus spike proteins found in the blood can indicate an active infection with SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19.⁴ High levels of virus spike proteins in the blood can be an indicator of severe disease and can help guide treatment decisions. Vaccine spike proteins, on the other hand, are a sign that the individual has been vaccinated and that their body is producing an immune response to the vaccine.²⁻³ The presence of vaccine spike proteins in the blood can indicate that the individual has developed immunity to the virus.

Discriminating between the two types of spike proteins is important for determining the current state of the disease in an individual, whether it is an active infection or the presence of an immune response after a vaccination. Additionally, it is crucial to differentiate the two types of spike proteins in order to avoid confusion and misinterpretation of results, which could lead to incorrect conclusions about the person's state of health and the need of further testing or treatment.

Most employed method to detect and discriminate between natural and vaccine spike proteins

Immunoenzymatic test

An immunoenzymatic test (also known as an ELISA test) to detect SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in blood typically involves the following steps:

- A sample of blood is taken from the individual being tested.
- The blood sample is then processed to isolate the antibodies (proteins that the immune system produces to fight off infections) that are specific to the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.
- A small amount of the isolated antibodies is then added to a plate that contains a fixed amount of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.
- The plate is then incubated for a period of time to allow the antibodies to bind to the spike protein, if present in the sample.
- A secondary antibody, which is conjugated to an enzyme, is then added to the plate. This secondary antibody will bind to the primary antibodies (the ones from the blood sample) that are already bound to the spike protein.
- The plate is then incubated again to allow the secondary antibody to bind.
- A colorimetric substrate is then added to the plate. The enzyme conjugated to the secondary antibody will then act on this substrate, resulting in a color change that indicates the presence of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in the blood sample.
- The intensity of the color change is measured and used to determine the amount of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein present in the sample.

Mass spectrometric test

Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is a technique that can be used to detect and quantify proteins in a sample, such as the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.⁵ It is a sensitive and specific method that can detect very low levels of proteins in a sample. In order to detect the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein using LC-MS, the sample is first prepared by enzymatic digestion. This process involves adding enzymes, such as trypsin, to the sample, which break down the proteins into smaller peptides. These peptides are then separated using liquid chromatography, which separates the different peptides based on their physical and chemical properties. After the peptides are separated, they are then analyzed using mass spectrometry. Mass spectrometry works by ionizing the peptides and then measuring their mass-to-

charge ratio. The mass-to-charge ratio is then used to identify the peptides and determine the presence of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in the sample. LC-MS is a powerful technique for detecting the presence of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in blood. It is able to detect very low levels of the spike protein and can also provide information about the quantity of the protein present. This is a very sensitive method that can be used to detect the virus at early stages of infection.

Immunoenzymatic Mass Spectrometry comparison

Immunoenzymatic technology, such as the ELISA test, is able to detect the presence of antibodies against the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in blood. This is because the test is designed to detect the binding between the spike protein and antibodies that are specific to it. However, the immunoenzymatic technology is not able to discriminate between the natural form of the spike protein and the form of the spike protein that is used in mRNA vaccines such as Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna. This is because both forms of the spike protein are structurally very similar, and the antibodies that are produced against them are also very similar. Therefore, the test cannot distinguish between the two forms of the spike protein. It is important to note that the mRNA vaccines do not infect the patient, they only instruct the cells to produce a spike protein that is similar to the natural form. The immune system then recognizes it as foreign and produces antibodies against it. Additionally, the mRNA vaccines have a different effect on the immune system than a natural infection. They don't replicate the virus in the body and therefore the immune response is different, with a higher titer of antibodies. It's important to note that the detection of antibodies against the spike protein can indicate past or recent exposure to the virus, however, it's not a 100% guarantee of immunity. Therefore, it is important to consider other factors, such as the individual's vaccination history and symptoms, when interpreting the results of an immunoenzymatic test for SARS-CoV-2.

Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is able to discriminate between the natural and vaccine forms of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein because it is a highly sensitive and specific technique that can detect very small differences in the peptide sequences of the two forms of the spike protein.⁶ When preparing the sample, the proteins are first digested using enzymes such as trypsin to produce a mixture of peptides. These peptides are then separated using liquid chromatography, and the separated peptides are analyzed using mass spectrometry. The mass spectrometer can determine the mass-to-charge ratio of the peptides, which can be used to identify the peptides and determine the sequence of amino acids that make up the protein (Fig 1.)

Fig 1. Trypsin is an enzyme belonging to the hydrolase class capable of reducing proteins to smaller polypeptides by means of proteolytic cuts with specificity for arginine (R) and lysine (K). Therefore, synthetic spike protein and natural spike protein can be discriminated as they produce different tryptic digestion products: PP-spike encoded by mRNA vaccines, when digested by trypsin, produces a LDPPEAEVQIDR (PP-spike marker) fragment. The wild-type SARS-CoV-2 protein, when digested by trypsin, produces two smaller fragments, namely LDK + VEAEVQIDR. More than 6,600,000 SARS-CoV-2 genomes have been sequenced and none of them appear to have any of the K986P and V987P mutations, including the Omicron variant.

The mRNA vaccines for SARS-CoV-2, such as Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna, use a slightly different sequence of amino acids for the spike protein than the natural form of the virus. This slight difference in the amino acid sequence results in a different mass-to-charge ratio for the peptides produced from the vaccine form of the spike protein than the natural form. By comparing the mass-to-charge ratios of the peptides originated from spike enzymatic digestion from the sample with those from a reference, LC-MS can detect these small differences in amino acid sequences and thus able to discriminate between the natural and vaccine forms of the spike protein. In the case of the spike proteins, the natural form of SARS-CoV-2 has an amino acid sequence of LDKVEAEVQIDR, while the sequence of the spike protein

used in some mRNA vaccines, such as Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna is LDPPEAEVQIDR (Fig. 2.). This slight difference in the amino acid sequence results in a different mass-to-charge ratio for the peptides produced from the vaccine form of the spike protein than the natural form.¹⁶ Tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) is a powerful analytical technique that can be used to selectively detect and identify specific peptides, such as LDKVEAEVQIDR and LDPPEAEVQIDR, in a sample.⁶ The information generated by the fragmentation, called product ions, can be used to determine the sequence of amino acids that make up the peptide. This allows the identification of the specific peptides of interest, such as

LDKVEAEVQIDR and LDPPEAEVQIDR, even in complex sample

Fig 2. In this image we can appreciate the substantial difference between the virus spike protein (wild-type) and the mRNA vaccines modified spike protein (Spike-PP). The difference is not only "primary structural" while the double proline induces a much more stable conformational state and with greater precision on the RBD portion of the protein, i.e. the more "active" portion which actually binds to the various receptors (ACE II, CD 147, etc.); the difference also lies in the post-transductional "pharmacokinetics" both for viral and "vaccine" ones. The viral Spike is produced in quantities sufficient to satisfy the completion of the viral architecture (virion) and NOT in excess, that from vmRNA has virtually no limits and is released "as is" into the circulation (in part). Furthermore, the Spike from vaccine mRNA has a stabilized "pre-fusion" conformation for a greater antibody attack. The problem is that this conformation makes the Spike protein always in the "active" conformation even towards the receptors that are normally "targets" of the viral spike.

A) The virus produce and has instructions (that transfer to the host cell machinery) to produce only the single component that occur for assembly it-self (S-protein included);

B) The nano-liposome containing the mRNA for the production of Spike glycoprotein do not stop only at the injection site but are spread throughout the body. The mRNA vaccine with the correct conditions is internalized in to the cells and begins to "make" the ribosomes produce the double Proline modified Spike protein (Spike-PP). The fate of this "neo-antigen" is apparently diversified (to date there are no reliable data on its intra and extra-cellular pharmacokinetics). A part is degraded by the proteasome, so that a short peptide fraction thereof can be assembled on the class I MHC

and recognized as "non-self" by CD8 CTL cells which attack the cell and kill themselves through apoptosis mechanism. Another way is the presentation of the full-length Spike at the trans-membrane level and hence the recognition and attachment by B lymphocytes and/or antibodies (with subsequent complement factors and/or NK cells attack); another hypothesis is the protein shedding which can occur in two ways: as it is and via exosomes. In these two cases it can occur for a portion of the protein (that is S1 or S2 subunit)^{7, 8, 9, 10, 11}.

Conclusion

Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is a highly sensitive and specific analytical technique that can be used to identify and quantify proteins in complex biological samples. The sensitivity and specificity of LC-MS/MS make it an ideal technique for identifying and quantifying the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in blood samples. The spike protein is a unique and highly conserved protein found on the surface of the virus and is responsible for its ability to infect host cells. The ability to accurately detect and quantify the spike protein in blood samples is important for determining whether an individual has been infected with the virus, and for monitoring the effectiveness of vaccines. In the case of SARS-CoV-2, LC-MS/MS is the reference technique to discriminate between natural and vaccine spike proteins in blood. The high sensitivity and specificity of LC-MS/MS allows for the accurate detection and quantification of the spike protein, even at very low concentrations. Additionally, LC-MS/MS can be used to distinguish between different forms of the spike protein, such as the natural form and the form that is produced by the vaccine. This is important for understanding the effectiveness of vaccines and for monitoring the spread of the virus in the population.

In conclusion, LC-MS/MS is the reference technique for discriminating natural and vaccine spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 in blood because it allows for the accurate detection and quantification of the spike protein, even at very low concentrations and it can distinguish between different forms of the spike protein.

Future perspective

- Understand exactly the presence of the vaccine spike protein in the body since the last injection;
- Understand if the antibodies produced by the vaccine have a neutralizing capacity also on the viral protein spike;
- Understand with a longitudinal analysis if the vaccine spike recurs or is in some way metabolized and excreted (probably through the urinary tract);
- Understand in adverse reactions whether the vaccine spike protein and/or viral spike protein are involved and how.

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